

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Yu**FIRST NAME:** Shaxuan**PROGRAM CODE:** MBAIF**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing the Basic (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-22)
4. What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One? (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
5. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-34)
6. Sample Corrections to Papers (EUCLID 2019, 36-43)
7. Chicago Style and Usage (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)

WRITING ESSAYS TO SUCCEED

1) INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of any scholar is to convey their opinion and inform the reader. The question is how to write a good essay, however. Writing a good essay is an art and skill that has to be learned and may take many years to capture the reader and convey efficiently one's message and intention. A crucial part of any essay writing is to conduct a proper literature review, maintain an appropriate style, ensure to follow the rules of grammar, and ensure that the essay content is authentic. To succeed in writing a good essay and conduct proper scholastic work, all these parameters need to be fulfilled (EUCLID 2019, 2-3). Even though one may use the best grammar, plagiarizing a work may lead to the essay's rejection and may be a stain on one's scholarly reputation. In the successive chapters, I will address the significant aspects of writing a proper essay and using a good style. More specifically, I will address the structure to effectively outline one's opinion and argument in an essay in the Response Paper. According to the encyclopedia, an essay is a relatively short literary composition where the writer discusses a subject matter that is typically scope restricted and aims at that the reader accepts a particular point of view (The Columbia Encyclopedia 2018). The study was assisted using the guidelines provided by Lisa Emerson (Emerson 2005, 5-10), and the recommendations outlined by Rebecca Stott in her practical guide to essay writing (Stott, Snaith and Rylance 2001, 1-10).

2) A BASIC APPROACH TO WRITING ESSAYS

Analysis of an essay's content is quintessential for any writer and plays an essential role in every step of writing. The most crucial part of writing is to analyze the topic that one wants to investigate and write about. This implies that one's knowledge about the topic is documented and that the main concepts are connected, such as in the form of a graph. A graph to structure the connections and relationships between the various topics is of great use for any writer in order to have an overview about the concepts at hand. It also allows to analyze the individual components and determine their relevance to the essay under consideration. As usual, it is crucial to really take into account the evidence that is provide and utilize it (EUCLID 2019, 3).

Though analysis seems to be a word for professional fields, it is a crucial activity which is being frequently conducted in many fields (Walden University 2020). It matters not only to our daily life's decision making but also it is vital for business, science, policy, etc. When one looks at the definition of analysis, then major parts in the definition are the decomposition of a topic or substance into smaller parts. This divide and conquer approach¹ is of paramount importance in a variety of areas. Having been used for thousands of years by great emperors that divided the enemy into smaller parts and then conquered the lands, the approach is essential for any scholar in order to address complex topics that are encountered some times. This methodology also applies to essay writing. We make up our thesis statement by analyzing the task to set the right tone for the essay at the very beginning. Based on the right direction, we conduct readings and researches. Through analysis, we have several findings to support the argument we have set at the very beginning. Then with the evidence and analysis, we can comment on the impact/meaning/recommendation to conclude our writing. The analysis is a continuing cycle in the process of essay writing, and it is essential to form a good essay.

3) WHY ESSAYS?

Essays are a great way for individuals to demonstrate their ability in fulfilling the subsequently discussed aspects. The main ability demonstrated in writing a proper essay is to understand the precise task set by the title and identify proper reading material related to the task (Turabian 2018, 3-8). The ability to understand the task ahead and determine appropriate referencing material is crucial for any individual, in particular students and researchers, to be able to express their opinions effectively and reason their thoughts about a particular topic. Doing so assists them in also structuring their essay such that they address possible counter-arguments by the reader (Harvey 2009, 1). Furthermore, in order to produce a high-quality essay, the writer needs to show their ability to understand and evaluate the used material as well as select the essential referral sources for the essay (Harvey 2009, 2). Given the abundance of publications and sources on the internet, this ability is highly important, requiring the writer to filter inadequate sources and focus on

¹ In latin: "divide et impera"

the core sources relevant to construct an effective argument in addition to achieving a well-supported conclusion (Stott, Snaith and Rylance 2001, 3).

The necessity to demonstrate these abilities make essays a very attractive instrument for tutors to teach individuals to outline their opinion in an incisive and clear written work. The limited size of the essay further requires the individual to focus on the core points, minimize descriptive writing, and avoid discussing non-relevant topics (Turabian 2018, 13).

4) HOW TO SUCCEED IN WRITING A HIGH-QUALITY ESSAY

Writing a high quality requires the writer sufficient time and dedication to achieve their goal to convince the reader to accept the writer's point of view. Critical here is that the writer starts to work early on the essay and ensures that sufficient time is available to carefully research and understand the task ahead, and then develop a strategy for the composition of the essay (Turabian 2018, 16). Helpful in this regard is defining questions posed in the essay and subsequently analyze the task ahead. This should then be followed by establishing an initial plan on how to structure one's thoughts and opinions as well as how to convey the point of view effectively in the essay (Turabian 2018, 54).

An extensive research phase is an essential pre-requisite for being able to compose a high-quality essay. Researching provides the essential knowledge to formulate a proper and well-developed argument for the essay (Turabian 2018, 17). Critical is to take notes during the reading process and evaluate read sections based on their usefulness for the argument. In taking the notes, one should always have the questions posed in mind and determine the relatedness of the information to the question. Hence the writer should strongly employ active reading techniques in order to attain a firm understanding of the ideas presented in the read material, as just compared to reading the words (McWhorter and Sember 2012, Chapter 1). Many students fail to realize the importance of active reading while doing research and hence fail to catch the researched material's central ideas.

Subsequently, the writer should organize the ideas outlining the central ideas that they want to address in the essay (Turabian 2018, 23). Important for effectively presenting an argument is to provide evidence to support it and avoid others presenting counter-arguments. One of the greatest challenges new writers face is that they have read lots of materials and many ideas. However, they fail to focus on the main arguments and present those concisely.

After having organized one's ideas, the writer may start to write the essay, thereby focusing on ensuring they follow the basic guidelines of starting with an introduction, encompass the main arguments in the body section of the essay and then finish it off with a strong conclusion where they concisely wrap up the main arguments (Turabian 2018, 64). In writing the essay, the writer should pay attention to proper referencing the ideas taken and avoid any forms of plainly copying quotes without providing proper citation remarks.

Plagiarism and plain copying are a serious offense and may lead to even lawsuits in both the academic and the corporate world.

The final part of writing a high-quality essay is to finish it off adequately and edit and format it according to the style requirements of the intended reader. Essential is hereby to revise the sentences to ensure that they can be easily understood and are concisely written, and incorporate transition signals such that the readers can follow one's arguments (Turabian 2018, 100). Also, ensure coherence in your essay as this is one of the major challenges new writers face.

Finally, the writer should read it through once more before submitting it and determine whether all the main aspects were addressed.

5) REFERENCING ESSENTIALS

Correct referencing is essential for ensuring the quality of the essay and providing credits to the work of others used for the development of the essay. Not giving proper credits to the author of a source is considered a serious offense in the academic as well as the corporate world and is defined as plagiarism (Turabian 2018, 128). Hence, the referencing and citation rules established by Kate Turabian shall both assist in leading individuals to properly reference sources and standardize the format on how to cite or reference. A frequently encountered form of referencing is reproducing a sentence or statement made by someone else. Literal reproduction in the essay requires the writer to put the statement into quotation marks and then subsequently put the author as well as referencing material into parentheses (Turabian 2018, 284). While reproducing the exact words of the author can in several cases lead to a very strong supporting argument, in particular, important quotes by famous people such as "Honesty is the first chapter in the book of wisdom" (Jefferson 2004), which can be used in the essay to outline the importance of in order to attain wisdom and be well-respected, one should aim to be honest.

While quotations may be rather powerful, one should avoid incorporating too many as this may lead to the perception that the writer just copies statements of various authors. In order to avoid this perception, paraphrasing the words of authors becomes the method of choice. Paraphrasing implies that the intended idea of the author is reproduced, however, that the writer is using one's own words and own style (Turabian 2018, 48). Even though the words are the writer's own, a reference to the work of the author is still required.

In referencing others' work, the Turabian style guide developed by Kate Turabian is frequently used in the social sciences. Impressive is that the distinguishing work written by Kate Turabian originated during her work as a secretary at the University of Chicago in the 1940s (The University of Chicago Press 2018). Not having a college degree, Kate was required to write a pamphlet for students outlining the college dissertations' correct styles. The school went so far as requiring that every master or doctoral thesis submitted by a student had to be checked by her to fulfil the style requirements (The University of Chicago Press 2018). The original book was further developed with several additions. The most

recent edition featured a revision focusing on building information literacy, taking into account that research nowadays has shifted online (Turabian 2018).

While the book focuses on part one primarily on conducting research and developing the material, part two aims to provide guidelines on how to cite properly (Turabian 2018). For most cases, the author-date citation style is preferred in the social sciences, which requires that the sources are briefly cited in the text using parentheses (Turabian 2018, 202). For the citation, typically, the author's name and year are put into the parentheses separated by a space. Each entry then matches up with the entry in the bibliography section, where the full reference information is provided. The citation requirements always emphasize the importance of defining in more detail on which page or in which section of the book, the information was retrieved from (Turabian 2018, 203). The page or section information should then be separated from the previous information via a comma.

6) CONCLUSION

The study material provided a thorough review of the main components of writing a proper essay, researching material, and what to take into account when properly citing resources. Writing an essay requires the writer to thoroughly research a topic and present their thoughts concisely and well-developed. Clearly having a specified structure in advance and understanding the material well is quintessential from transforming a mediocre essay to a high-quality one. Personally, the study material has again outlined the importance of carefully researching the area to develop a solid essay and arguments to convince the reader of one's idea. Additionally, a structure should need to be in place before starting to write the essay to ensure the essay's coherence.

Finally, the main citation guidelines based on the Turabian style guide were presented. The Turabian style was initially developed in the 1930s at the University of Chicago and has ever since been one of the main guidelines for writing thesis and papers. The guideline addresses both the research phase and what aspects are important to take into account and stipulates the citation rules that have to be followed to ensure a standardized format and make it easier for others to follow.

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